

THE EPOXY BEHAVIOR OF CFRP ACCORDING TO CLEARANCE AND PRESSURE IN COMPRESSION MOLDING FOR U-CHANNEL

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1 Introduction

Recently in automobile, aerospace and other transport industries, the importance of energy saving and high mileage is being emphasized due to depletion of existing fossil energy. Due to such issues, weight lightening of transportation mode is essential and usage of fiber reinforced composite materials is being increased [1-3].

Among the many fiber reinforced composite materials, CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastic) that has high strength and high rigidity is the most attractive composite material, which is why researches on basic properties of this material are continually being conducted [4-5].

However, composites are anisotropic materials that have differing properties according to the direction of fiber arrangement [6] and are comprised of reinforcements and matrices. As such, their mechanical properties change according to fraction of reinforcement and numerous studies have been conducted in relation to fraction of reinforcement [7-8].

Heru S.B. et al[8] studied the effects of fracture during application of tension according to the fiber fraction of unidirectional carbon/epoxy composites. Testing by adjusting fiber fraction to be 30~70% showed that boundary separation between fibers was the dominant cause for fracture in high fiber fraction whereas fracture of the fiber was the dominant fracture mode in low fiber fraction. G. Wrobel et al [9] revealed by quantitatively analyzing distribution of fiber fraction in CFRP composites that thermal diffusivity is different according to carbon fracture fraction and that there are differences in thermal diffusivity according to the thickness of the matrix as well. In addition, O. I. OKOLI et al [10] studied

how volume percent and strain rate of fiber affect the matrix fracture of the composite materials.

The mechanical properties of CFRP are greatly affected by the fractions of reinforcements and matrices. When producing CFRP products, autoclave or vacuum bag techniques are used to obtain a uniform thickness and fiber fraction in the overall product. However, shortcomings of the aforementioned two techniques include a time-consuming molding process, and difficulty in molding thicker products.

The technique used to resolve such problems is hot compression molding. While negative atmospheric pressure is applied under a vacuum state for autoclave or vacuum bag molding, fast molding is made possible in the case of hot compression molding, together with possibility of molding thicker products with a short curing time by applying positive atmospheric pressure with a press.

Moreover, a uniform thickness and fiber fraction of the products are possible when molding plain plate products. However, car bodies and aerospace components are typically three-dimensional shape products and researches on product with any shape are few except plain sheet. When hot compression molding is used for the shape products, there may be differences between the pressure received by the CFRP prepreg from the press of the punch and lower die, and the pressure received by the CFRP prepreg due to tolerance between the punch and lower die. Nonuniform pressures may cause differences in mechanical properties due to nonuniform fiber fractions and thickness differences in CFRP products. In order to apply the hot compression molding technique, studies according to the fiber fraction of the products, depending on the

experimental parameters when making CFRP products with any shape, and the evaluation of mechanical properties according to thickness, are needed.

Accordingly, in this study, a U-channel CFRP was produced by hot compression molding with pressure and clearance as parameters. The epoxy fraction was measured according to changes between pressed positions and non-pressed positions. Thickness changes of products were compared by measuring a thinning rate according to positions on the U-channel CFRP through the epoxy fraction according to pressure and clearance. Furthermore, the effects of pressure and clearance on the epoxy flow, and their subsequent mechanisms, were studied by staining the epoxy with colorant in order to macroscopically observe the actual epoxy flow.

2 Experimental

2.1 Preparation of specimen

CFRP used in the experiment was carbon fiber of Toray Company in which plain fiber was used, and prepreg was thermosetting resin with initial epoxy weight percent of 35%. Table 1 shows data on properties of the epoxy. Thickness of one layer of CFRP was 0.3mm and five layers of 180 x 130mm in size were stacked on top of each other.

Fig. 1(a) shows U-channel mold that was used for CFRP production. During hot compression molding, cartridge heater was used to heat the mold to 140°C after which the specimen was pressed for 30 minutes. For the lower die, the mold was constructed to allow tolerance between punch and die to be adjustable by designing the die on the side positions to be movable. By adjusting tolerance between punch and die (d_o) to be 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0mm, clearance of die on side positions and punch was varied to be 0.7, 1 and 1.3, and pressure (P_p) was varied to be 0.05 and 0.5MPa in making the U-shaped CFRP. (t_o is 1.5mm, which is thickness of initial 5-ply CFRP, and d_o is the tolerance between punch and die.) Fig. 1(b) shows the U-shaped CFRP that has been cured after hot compression molding and also illustrates pressed positions and non-pressed side positions.

Item	YD-115J	Test method
EEW(g/eq)	175-194	KD-AS-001
Viscosity(cps at 25°C)	150-500	KD-AS-005
Hy-Cl(wt.%)	0.6-0.9	KD-AS-010
Specific Gravity	1.14	KD-AS-040

Table.1 Epoxy resin (Bisphenol-A)

(a) Punch and die for U-channel mold

(b) U-shape CFRP

Fig.1 experimental apparatus for hot compression molding

(a) Experiment for measuring epoxy weight percent

(b) Experiment for epoxy flow macroscopically

Fig.2 Schematic diagram of experiment

2.2 Measuring epoxy weight percent

Fig. 2 shows schematic diagram of the experiment. As shown in Fig. 2(a), U-shaped CFRP was constructed through hot compression molding after which epoxy weight percent (Wt) and properties were measured through three-point bending by cutting the bending specimen according to positions. In order to check the epoxy weight percent (Wt) according to the clearance (C) and punch pressure (Pp), weight of initial epoxy quantity (35%) was measured and then epoxy weight that had either increased or decreased was measured using electronic scale by symmetrically cutting each of the positions in U-shaped CFRP into sizes of 10 x 10mm.

In order to check thinning rate(γ) at each position according to the clearance (C) and punch pressure (Pp), bending specimen thickness were measured.

2.3 Macroscopic observation of epoxy flow

Fig. 2(b) shows experiment for macroscopic observation of epoxy flow by adding colorant into the epoxy. To macroscopically observe the epoxy flow, one to two percent of colorant was mixed into the epoxy to provide color. The epoxy flow was macroscopically observed to understand how epoxy flow changes according to pressure (Pp) and clearance (C). Then, the epoxy behaving mechanism was analyzed by examining the epoxy flow.

3. Experiment results and discussion

3.1 Epoxy weight percent according to pressure and clearance

Fig. 3(a)~(b) show changes in epoxy weight percent (Wt) after hot compression molding the prepreg that had initial epoxy weight percent (Wi) of

35% according to changes in pressure (Pp) and clearance (C). Pressed positions are numbers one, four to six and nine while side positions are two to three and seven to eight. When C=0.7, noticeably low epoxy weight percent (Wt) was observed in side positions regardless of Pp=0.0 and 0.5MPa. This is because high volumes of epoxy flowed out of the mold due to pressure between punch and die and friction during molding when C<1.0. Reduction of epoxy weight percent in side positions signifies reduction of thickness.

When C=0.7, there was almost no difference in epoxy weight percent (Wt) according to pressure (Pp) and when pressure (Pp) was high, it was observed that epoxy weight percent (Wt) for pressed position three increased instead. However when C=1.0 and 1.3, there was clear difference in epoxy weight percent between pressed positions one, four to six and nine according to pressure (Pp). For pressed positions four to six in the center, epoxy weight percent (Wt) decreased from 25~27% to 22~24% when pressure increased from 0.05MPa to 0.5MPa and when C=1.0 and it decreased from 30~34% to 20~21% when C=1.3. In both cases of C=1.0 and 1.3, epoxy weight percent (Wt) decreased to 12~15% due to increased pressure for pressed positions one and nine.

On the other hand, when C=1.0 and 1.3, there was not much difference in terms of pressure for side positions two to three and seven to eight. Instead, it was observed that epoxy weight percent (Wt) slightly increased when pressure (Pp) increased to 0.5MPa. Possible reason for this is that when Pp=0.05MPa, epoxy in the side positions two to three and seven to eight was able to flow to the center positions four to six by gravity but as pressure increased by factor of ten to Pp=0.5MPa, thickness became thinner, which forbade flow to center positions four to six. It was made known that epoxy weight percent (Wt) decreased due to high quantities of epoxy flowed outside the mold from the pressed positions one and nine as pressure increased.

(a) $P_p=0.05\text{MPa}$

(b) $P_p=0.5\text{MPa}$

Fig.3 Epoxy weight percent of U-shape CFRP at each position

(a) $P_p=0.05\text{MPa}$

Fig.4 Thinning rate of U-shape CFRP at each position

3.2 Thinning rate according to the pressure and clearance

Fig. 4 shows thinning rate (γ) according to pressure (P_p) and clearance (C). The effects of epoxy weight percent (W_t) on the thickness of U-shaped CFRP can be known through Fig. 3 (a)~(b) and Fig. 4 (a)~(b). As pressure increased from 0.05MPa to 0.5MPa, thinning rate (γ) for pressed position number three decreased from 13% to 10% having increased thickness when $C=0.7$ while thinning rates (γ) for pressed positions one and five each increased from 23% and 17% to 30% and 28%, respectively, having decreased thickness. In case of side positions two and four, thinning rates stayed at 26% and 23%, respectively, as the pressure increased, showing no differences. This is congruent to Fig. 3 (a)~(b) that showed almost no changes in epoxy weight percent (W_t).

As pressure increased from 0.05MPa to 0.5MPa, graph shows that thinning rate decreases as epoxy weight percent (W_t) increases and that thinning rate (γ) increases when epoxy weight percent (W_t) decreases as shown in Fig. 3(a)~(b) and Fig. 4 (a)~(b) when $C=1.0$.

However when $C=1.3$ according to changes in pressure, different effect took place in side positions two and four from when $C=1.0$. When $C=1.3$, C is greater than 1 and so side positions two and four are not pressed by the punch and die. Despite the epoxy weight percent (W_t) for side positions two to three and seven to eight being less than the initial W_t of 35% as shown in Fig. 3 (a)~(b), it can be seen from

Fig.5 Epoxy flow of U-shape CFRP after curing according to pressure and clearance

Fig. 4 (a)~(b) that thinning rate (γ) is negative for side positions two and four when $C=1.3$. This means that the thickness increased more than the prepreg. The reason why thickness for non-pressed side positions two and four increased and yet is less than initial epoxy weight percent signifies that inter-layer adhesion is insufficient due to lack of receiving side pressure and that the bonding force between the layers is poor.

3.3 Macroscopic observation of epoxy and the epoxy flow mechanism

In order to macroscopically observe the epoxy flow of U-shaped CFRP after curing, product was

produced by impregnating epoxy mixed with colorant into carbon fiber. Fig. 5 shows the U-shaped CFRP after hot compression molding of prepreg, which is impregnated color epoxy.

When observing the epoxy flow according to clearance (C), the red epoxy that was in the side position moves to the top due to friction between punch and die during molding when $C=0.7$ as shown in Fig. 5 (a). Because clearance (C) is small, large amounts of epoxy flows to the top and so there was red epoxy present even in the round area (R area) between number one and two and eventually the red epoxy passed number one and flowed out of the mold as shown in Fig. 5 (a).

Fig.6 Mechanism of epoxy flow according to pressure and clearance

When $C=1.0$, it can be observed that the red epoxy is blended with the white epoxy in the side area number two as shown in Fig. 5 (b). It is clear that the epoxy which flowed downward due to gravity during molding concentrated in the lower area and its thickness increased, which eventually flowed to the top due to side friction of punch and die even if $d_o = t_o$. However, the red epoxy did not pass numbers one and two and leave the mold as it was with $C=0.7$.

When $C=1.3$, it can be understood that the red epoxy could not flow to the top as shown in Fig. 5 (c) number two since tolerance (d_o) is greater than five-ply CFRP (t_o). It can be observed that the side area of U-shaped CFRP did not cure vertically as it was with Fig. 5 (a) and (b) but instead cured in an inclined angle to the side due to large clearance. Observation of epoxy flow according to pressure (P_p) shows that $T_d=140^\circ\text{C}$ just as in Fig.5 (d) and (e). In addition, comparing the cases with the two different pressures (P_p) of 0.05MPa and 0.5MPa when $C=0.7$ showed that pressure does not affect epoxy flow as much as clearance. Instead of pressure affecting the direction of the epoxy flow, it was observed that large amounts of epoxy flowed outside the mold during molding when pressure was 0.5MPa compared to 0.05MPa. Comparison of Fig.5 (d) and

Fig. 5 (e) shows that the original CFRP color was present due to lightened epoxy color since large amounts of epoxy flowed out of the mold in case of Fig. 5 (e) that had pressure of 0.5MPa. Also, it was also observed that large amounts of epoxy were trapped and hardened in punch R area of side position number four as shown in Fig. 5 (e).

Fig. 6 shows epoxy flow mechanism based on the macroscopic observation and epoxy weight percent (Wt) graph (Fig. 3). When $C=0.7$, red epoxy that was in the side positions received pressure from between the punch and die from the beginning and it rose to the top due to friction during molding, which caused epoxy flow as described in Fig. 6(a) and (d). Due to such epoxy flow, it can be noted for both ends of pressed positions one and nine that the epoxy weight percent (Fig. 3) was greater and thinning rate (Fig. 4) was less than when the clearance conditions were 1.0 and 1.3. When $C=1.0$, it cannot pass by the R area of the die and leave the mold despite the epoxy in the side positions slightly swelling as shown in Fig. 6 (b) and (e). As presented in Fig. 3(a)-(b), it can be observed that epoxy fraction in side positions two to three and seven to eight is greater than the one for $C=0.7$.

When $C=1.3$, epoxy increases in the side positions since tolerance (d_o) is greater than five-ply CFRP

(t0) as shown in Fig. 6 and there is less amount of epoxy flowing out of the mold from the side positions compared to the case of C=1.0. (Fig.3)

When comparing the cases with pressure (Pp) of 0.05MPa and 0.5MPa, it can be understood that the effects of pressure on the epoxy flow is not as great as the effects from the clearance. Instead of pressure affecting the direction of the epoxy flow, high amounts of epoxy flowed out of the mold during molding when pressure was 0.5MPa compared to the case of 0.05MPa. As shown in the two cases presented in Fig. 6(a)~(c) and Fig. 6(d)~(f), there was not much difference in the epoxy flow of CFRP and instead the difference was in the epoxy that flowed out of the mold. This explained that the epoxy flow of a product is dominated by the clearance (C) and that the pressure (Pp) influences the overall epoxy impregnation percent inside the CFRP.

4. Conclusion

1. When C= 1.0 and 1.3, epoxy fraction in pressed positions reduced significantly compared to the ones of side positions when pressure became 0.5MPa from 0.05MPa. When C=0.7, there was not much difference in epoxy fraction due to pressure.

2. Thinning rate distribution showed thinning rate of 20~27% for positions one to five except number three when clearance was 0.7. When clearance was 1.0, thinning rate for side positions was lower than the one of pressed positions. In case of C=1.3, it was observed that thickness of side positions increased instead.

3. It can be made known that epoxy flow dominant over the clearance through the macroscopic observation of epoxy flow and flow mechanism. Also, it was understood that high pressure causes the high quantities of epoxy to flow outside the mold.

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